

Sample 15a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0022
	{Si}	79.7
	{Ca}	4.5
	{Al, Si}	4.2
	{Ti}	2.0
	{Al, Si, K}	1.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	1.6
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.2
	{Fe}	1.0
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.0
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.6
	{Si, K}	0.5
	{Si, Fe}	0.4
	{Na, Si}	0.3
	{Mg, Si}	0.2
	{Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
	{Mg, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{P, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, P, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Al}	0.1
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.0
	{Mg}	0.0
	{S, Ca}	0.0
	{Al, Ca}	0.0
	{Na, S}	0.0
	{Cl}	0.0
	{Cl}	0.0
	{Zn-LA1}	0.0
	{S}	0.0
	{S, Ba-LA1}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	0.7
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.1
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	0.2
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.0
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.2
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	11.8
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.6
Carbon rich - other	3.7
Cement or BOF converter	3.4
Cement	3.1
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.8
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	71.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	4.5
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	0.8
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	0.2
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.0
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	0.2
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	11.8
Site - carbon-rich other	0.6
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	3.7
Urban, rarely site - slag	3.4
Urban	3.8
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	71.0
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	4.5
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 15b

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0024
	{Si}	74.0
	{Al, Si}	6.3
	{Na, Al, Si}	4.5
	{Al, Si, K}	2.9
	{Ca}	2.5
	{Na, Si}	1.6
	{Fe}	1.3
	{Ti}	1.3
	{Si, Ca LoP}	1.1
	{Si, Ca HiP}	0.9
	{Si, K}	0.6
	{S, Ca}	0.4
	{Mg, Si}	0.4
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Mg, Ca}	0.3
	{Si, Fe}	0.3
	{Al}	0.2
	{Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Na, S}	0.1
	{Si, P, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.0
	{Zn-LA1}	0.0
	{Al, Ca}	0.0
	{Cl}	0.0
	{Cl}	0.0
	{S}	0.0
	{Mg}	0.0
	{Ca, Fe}	0.0
	{P}	0.0
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.0
	{Si, P}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	0.1
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.5
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	0.0
BOF converter slag slopping	0.8
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.1
Desulph slag	0.1
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.3
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.8
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.3
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	10.3
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.2
Carbon rich - other	2.0
Cement or BOF converter	1.2
Cement	2.1
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.2
Ti-rich paint	2.2
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	76.7
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	2.1
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

141 μm

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	0.5
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	1.0
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.3
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.8
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.3
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	10.3
Site - carbon-rich other	0.2
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	2.0
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.2
Urban	4.5
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	76.7
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	2.1
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

141 μm

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 15c

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0015
{Si}	80.2
{Ca}	5.6
{Al, Si}	5.5
{Al, Si, K}	1.4
{Si, Ca LoP}	1.3
{Fe}	0.9
{Si, Ca HiP}	0.8
{Na, Al, Si}	0.7
{Si, Fe}	0.5
{Al, Si, Ca}	0.4
{Si, K}	0.3
{Na, Si}	0.2
{Ti}	0.2
{Mg, Ca}	0.2
{S, Ca}	0.2
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.2
{Al}	0.2
{Mg, Si}	0.2
{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
{Si, Cl}	0.1
{Si, Fe}	0.1
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.1
{Al, Si, Cl}	0.1
{Al, Ca}	0.0
{Na, Si, Cl}	0.0
{Cl}	0.0
{S}	0.0
{Al, Si, Fe}	0.0
{Cl}	0.0
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.0
{P, Ca}	0.0
{Al, Si, Ti}	0.0
{Mg}	0.0
{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	0.8
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.2
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.1
BOF converter slag	0.2
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.1
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.3
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.4
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	7.9
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.9
Carbon rich - other	2.0
Cement or BOF converter	2.8
Cement	2.4
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	77.3
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	3.4
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	0.9
Site - ore / hot metal	0.1
Site - slag	0.3
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.3
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	1.4
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	7.9
Site - carbon-rich other	0.9
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	2.0
Urban, rarely site - slag	2.8
Urban	2.5
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	77.3
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	3.4
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels